

Status of CELLAR
FFV1 & Matroska

@dericed 2018-10-25 #nttw3

MediaConch

Checker Policies Display Settings

Policy list:

Search

- User policies
 - Is this NTSC or PAL SD? (and)
 - Is Width at 720?
 - Is this NTSC SD or PAL SD? (or)
 - Is this PAL? (and)
 - PAL FrameRate
 - PAL Height
 - Is this NTSC? (and)
 - NTSC FrameRate?
 - NTSC Height?
 - Best Practices or Good Enough Practices? (and)
 - Digitization Policy (and)
 - Are these file types supported by my archive? (and)
- System policies

Rule type: MediaInfo MicroMedia

Rule name:

Track type *:

Field *:

Occurrence:

Validator:

Value *:

Fields marked by asterisks (*) are required

Check by file upload Check online files Check server files

Policy: Display: Verbosity:

Results

Apply a policy to all results:

Show: entries Search:

Files	Implem	Policy	MediaInfo	MediaTrace	Status
ffv1_test_pixfmt-yuv444p10le...	✓ Valid	✗ Matroska is well described?	👁️ ⚙️	👁️ ⚙️	✓
ffv1_test_pixfmt-yuva422p_co...	✓ Valid	✗ Matroska is well described?	👁️ ⚙️	👁️ ⚙️	✓
ffv1_test_pixfmt-yuva444p_co...	👁️ ⚙️	👁️ ⚙️	👁️ ⚙️	👁️ ⚙️	🔄
veraPDF test suite 6-1-10-t0...	✗ Not valid	✗ Matroska is well described?	👁️ ⚙️	👁️ ⚙️	✓
train1.tif	✗ Not valid	✗ Matroska is well described?	👁️ ⚙️	👁️ ⚙️	✓
buggy_header.pdf	✗ Not valid	✗ Matroska is well described?	👁️ ⚙️	👁️ ⚙️	✓

Showing 11 to 16 of 16 entries

Previous 1 2

The Working Group will seek consensus and refinements for specifications for both FFV1 and Matroska in order to provide authoritative, standardized specifications for users and developers. Backward compatibility with existing versions 0-3 of the FFV1 and Matroska specifications will be an important goal, while also reviewing and refining the current version 4 under active development. Although not encouraged, non-backwards-compatible changes to the input specifications will be acceptable if the Working Group determines that the modifications are required to meet the group's technical objectives, provided that the reasons for these changes are clearly documented.

Deliverables:

- Informational specification for Matroska container format versions 1, 2 and 3 to IESG for publication
- Standards Track specification for Matroska container format version 4 to IESG for publication
- Informational specification for FFV1 video codec versions 0, 1 and 3 to IESG for publication
- Standards Track specification for FFV1 video codec version 4 to IESG for publication
- Standards Track specification for FLAC audio codec to IESG for publication

FFmpeg / FFV1

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Code Issues 4 Pull requests 4 Projects 0 Wiki Insights

The FFV1 lossless video codec specification.

303 commits 1 branch 9 releases 8 contributors

Branch: master New pull request Create new file Upload files Find file Clone or download

dericed and Michael Niedermayer bump version to ffv1-05, ffv1-v4-02 Latest commit a073ab1 8 days ago

.gitignore	upgrading to a working group document	a year ago
Makefile	bump version to ffv1-05, ffv1-v4-02	7 days ago
README.md	add link to version 4	7 days ago
ffv1.md	titlecase/tilde-quote Line,Plane,Sample,Pixel	9 days ago
pdf_backmatter.md	pdf_backmatter.md - updates dead links	2 years ago
pdf_frontmatter.md	move pdf frontmatter to separate header file	2 years ago
rfc_frontmatter.md	bump version to ffv1-05, ffv1-v4-02	7 days ago
style.css	CSS stylesheet now locally available	3 years ago

Matroska-Org / matroska-specification

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No description or website provided.

matroska file-format specification

528 commits 52 branches 7 releases 1 environment 18 contributors View license

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robUx4 live streams are not "broadcast" streams Latest commit 98c65bf 3 days ago

_includes	Drop the word "Guidelines" from the element ordering section	9 months ago
_layouts	cleans up html for webpage rendering, removes unneeded lay...	a year ago
_sass	poc jekyll with default jekyll theme	3 years ago
codec	av1: [decode_tile] smaller than 16 bytes are not encrypted	14 days ago
css	adds sidebar and makes specification index page (as on origin...	2 years ago
tools	libmatroska verifier: also verify element IDs match expected cl...	a year ago
transforms	use recurring attribute	21 days ago
.gitignore	bump to wg doc version 00	3 months ago
CODE_OF_CONDUCT.md	use the same term to tell there has been modifications to the ...	11 months ago
LICENSE.md	move the `layout: default` outside of each Markdown file	a year ago
Makefile	bump to mkv 01	3 months ago
README.md	README - adds xsltproc dependency	3 months ago
_config.yml	split the documentation in 3 parts	a year ago
attachments.md	makes section names unique; removes dupe Laced Data secti...	10 months ago
chapters.md	rename timecode* to timestamp*	9 months ago
codec_specs.md	add a reference for A_PCM/FLOAT/IEEE audio	22 days ago
cues.md	makes section names unique; removes dupe Laced Data secti...	10 months ago
diagram.md	rename timecode* to timestamp*	9 months ago
ebml_matroska.xml	live streams are not "broadcast" streams	a day ago
feed.xml	poc jekyll with default jekyll theme	3 years ago
index_codec.md	bump to wg doc version 00	3 months ago
index_matroska.md	bump to mkv 01	3 months ago
index_tags.md	bump to wg doc version 00	3 months ago
logo.png	adds sidebar and makes specification index page (as on origin...	2 years ago
matroska_schema_secti...	adjust text to move element descriptions up a level and limit s...	3 months ago
matroska_tags.xml	update some web addresses	9 months ago
menu.md	rename timecode* to timestamp*	9 months ago

Matroska-Org / ebml-specification

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Code Issues 3 Pull requests 0 Projects 0 Wiki Insights

the specification for the EBML format

410 commits 25 branches 6 releases 11 contributors CC-BY-4.0

Branch: master New pull request Create new file Upload files Find file Clone or download

robUx4 DocTypeExtensionName: An => A Latest commit 85e05e 28 days ago

.gitignore	Makefile: rename merged.md into draft-ietf-cellar-ebml-01.md	2 years ago
CODE_OF_CONDUCT.md	use the same term to tell there has been modifications to the original	11 months ago
EBMLSchema.xsd	linewrap the xml examples	a year ago
LICENSE.markdown	add a README and the CC BY 4.0 license	4 years ago
Makefile	bump work version to 08	28 days ago
README.markdown	Add the Contributor Covenant code of conduct	11 months ago
ebml_schema_example.xml	Document how to constrain EBML Header elements in the EBML Schema	a year ago
index.markdown	rename specification to index	4 years ago
rfc_frontmatter.markdown	bump work version to 08	28 days ago

Introduction

`EBML`, short for Extensible Binary Meta Language, specifies (byte) aligned format inspired by the principle of XML (a fraction of data).

The goal of this document is to define a generic, binary, space-efficient format that can be used to define more complex formats (such as content) using an `EBML Schema`. The definition of the `EBML` idea behind HTML and XML as a good one: separate structure and semantics into the same structural layer to be used with multiple, possibly different semantic layers. Except for the `EBML Header` and a few global specifications, the `EBML` format specification is intended to define how other `EBML`-based formats are defined.

`EBML` uses a simple approach of building `Elements` upon their length, and value) as this approach is well known, easy to parse, and selective data parsing. The `EBML` structure additionally allows for an arrangement to support complex structural formats in an efficient manner.

Notation and Conventions

The key words "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL" in this document are interpreted as described in [RFC2119].

This document defines specific terms in order to define the format of `EBML`. Specific terms are defined below:

`Child Element`: A `Child Element` is a relative term to describe `Elements` immediately contained within a `Master Element`.

`EBML`: Extensible Binary Meta Language

`Element Data`: The value(s) of the `EBML Element` which is identified by the `Element ID` and the `Element Data Size`. The format of the `Element Data` is defined in this document and the corresponding `EBML Schema` of the `Element`.

`Element Data Size`: An expression, encoded as a `Variable String`, that defines the length in octets of the `Element Data`.

`EBML Body`: All data of an `EBML Document` following the `EBML Header` is considered the `EBML Body`.

[[Docs](#)] [[txt](#)] [[pdf](#)] [[xml](#)] [[html](#)] [[Tracker](#)] [[WG](#)] [[Email](#)] [[Diff1](#)] [[Diff2](#)] [[Nits](#)]

Versions: ([draft-lhomme-cellar-ebml](#)) 00

cellar

S. Lhomme

Internet-Draft

Intended status: Standards Track

D. Rice

Expires: March 27, 2017

M. Bunkus

September 23, 2016

Extensible Binary Meta Language draft-ietf-cellar-ebml-00

Abstract

This document defines the Extensible Binary Meta Language (EBML) format as a generalized file format for any type of data in a hierarchical form. EBML is designed as a binary equivalent to XML and utilizes a storage-efficient approach to building nested Elements with identifiers, lengths, and values. Similar to how an XML Schema defines the structure and semantics of an XML Document, this document defines an EBML Schema to convey the semantics of an EBML Document.

Status of This Memo

This Internet-Draft is submitted in full conformance with the provisions of [BCP 78](#) and [BCP 79](#).

Internet-Drafts are working documents of the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF). Note that other groups may also distribute working documents as Internet-Drafts. The list of current Internet-Drafts is at <http://datatracker.ietf.org/drafts/current/>.

Internet-Drafts are draft documents valid for a maximum of six months and may be updated, replaced, or obsoleted by other documents at any time. It is inappropriate to use Internet-Drafts as reference material or to cite them other than as "work in progress."

This Internet-Draft will expire on March 27, 2017.

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draft-ietf-cellar-ebml-07 Extensible Binary Meta Language	2018-09-25 42 pages	I-D Exists In WG Last Call: Informational <i>Aug 2018</i>			
draft-ietf-cellar-ffv1-06 FFV1 Video Coding Format Version 0, 1, and 3	2018-10-18 43 pages New	I-D Exists WG Document Reviews: artart, genart, secdir <i>Oct 2018</i>			
draft-ietf-cellar-ffv1-v4-03 FFV1 Video Coding Format Version 4	2018-10-18 42 pages New	I-D Exists WG Document <i>Dec 2018</i>			
draft-ietf-cellar-matroska-01 Matroska Specifications	2018-07-26 165 pages	I-D Exists WG Document <i>Apr 2019</i>			
draft-ietf-cellar-tags-00 Matroska Tags	2018-07-17 20 pages	I-D Exists WG Document			

<https://datatracker.ietf.org/wg/cellar/documents/>

[WIP] Add Color Filter Array (Bayer) #100

JeromeMart... wants to merge 1 commit into FFmpeg:master from MediaArea:RGGb

Conversation 43 Commits 1 Checks 0 Files changed 1

Changes from all commits - Jump to... +41 -7

Diff settings Review changes -

```
48 ffv1.md Show comments View
```

```
@@ -294,7 +294,7 @@ Background: in first implementations of FFV1 bitstream, the index
for Cb and Cr
```

```
294 294
295 295 ## Color spaces
296 296
297 - FFV1 supports two color spaces: YCbCr and RGB. Both color spaces allow an optional
Alpha `Plane` that can be used to code transparency data.
297 + FFV1 supports several color spaces. Both color spaces allow an optional Alpha `Plane`
that can be used to code transparency data.
298 298
299 299 The FFV1 bitstream interleaves data in an order determined by the color space. In
YCbCr for each `Plane`, each `Line` is coded from top to bottom and for each `Line`,
each `Sample` is coded from left to right. In JPEG2000-RCT for each `Line` from top to
bottom, each `Plane` is coded and for each `Plane`, each `Sample` is encoded from left
to right.
300 300
@@ -395,6 +395,10 @@ In JPEG2000-RCT, the coding order would be left to right and then
top to bottom,
```

```
395 395
396 396 Y[1,1] Y[2,1] Cb[1,1] Cb[2,1] Cr[1,1] Cr[2,1] Y[1,2] Y[2,2] Cb[1,2] Cb[2,2] Cr[1,2]
Cr[2,2]
397 397
398 + ### Color Filter Array
399 +
400 + (TODO)
401 +
398 402 ## Coding of the Sample Difference
399 403
400 404 Instead of coding the n+1 bits of the Sample Difference with Huffman or Range coding
(or n+2 bits, in the case of JPEG2000-RCT), only the n (or n+1, in the case of
JPEG2000-RCT) least significant bits are used, since this is sufficient to recover the
original `Sample`. In the equation below, the term "bits" represents
bits_per_raw_sample+1 for JPEG2000-RCT or bits_per_raw_sample otherwise:
@@ -722,6 +726,10 @@ Parameters( ) {
722 726 for ( i = 1; i < 256; i++)
723 727 state_transition_delta[ i ] | sr
724 728 colorspace_type | ur
729 + if (colorspace_type == 2) {
730 + for ( i = 0; i < 4; i++) {
731 + cfa_pattern [ i ] | ur
732 + }
725 733 if (version >= 1)
726 734 bits_per_raw_sample | ur
727 735 chroma_planes | br
```

```
815 - |value | color space losslessly encoded | transformation |
interleave method |
816 - |-----|:-----|:-----|:-----|:-----|
817 - | 0 | YCbCr | No Pixel transformation | `Plane`
then `Line` |
818 - | 1 | RGB | JPEG2000-RCT | `Line`
then `Plane` |
819 - | Other | reserved for future use | reserved for future use |
reserved for future use |
823 + |value | color space encoded | pixel transformation | extra plane content
| interleave method |
824 + |-----|:-----|:-----|:-----|:-----|
825 + | 0 | YCbCr | None | Transparency
| `Plane` then `Line` |
826 + | 1 | RGB | JPEG2000-RCT | Transparency
| `Line` then `Plane` |
827 + | 2 | Color Filter Array | JPEG2000-RCT | Color difference
| `Line` then `Plane` |
828 + | Other | reserved for future use | reserved for future use | reserved for future use
| reserved for future use |
820 829 Restrictions:
821 830 If `colorspace_type` is 1, then `chroma_planes` MUST be 1, `log2_h_chroma_subsample`
MUST be 0, and `log2_v_chroma_subsample` MUST be 0.
822 831 + If `colorspace_type` is 2, then `chroma_planes` MUST be 1, `log2_h_chroma_subsample`
MUST be 0, and `log2_v_chroma_subsample` MUST be 0, transparency MUST be 1.
832 +
833 +
834 + ### cfa_pattern
835 +
836 + `cfa_pattern` indicates the actual color filter array geometric pattern of the image
sensor used to capture the single sensor color image.
837 + The pattern has a fixed size of 4 values (fixed width of 2, fixed height of 2) and is
provided per line top to bottom, and for each line left to right.
838 +
839 + |value | color |
840 + |-----|:-----|:-----|:-----|:-----|
841 + | 0 | red |
842 + | 1 | green |
843 + | 2 | blue |
844 +
845 + Restrictions:
846 + At least 1 component of each color MUST be present.
847 +
848 + As an example, a typical pattern is 0112, which implies:
849 +
850 +
851 + +-----+
852 + | R | G |
853 + +-----+
854 + | G | B |
855 + +-----+
856 +
823 857
```

Filters is:issue is:open Labels Milestones

New issue

3 Open ✓ 20 Closed	Author	Labels	Projects	Milestones	Assignee	Sort
mean,k estimate for Golomb Rice #118 opened on Jul 6 by dericed						4
[v4] implementation of additional image data #47 opened on Jan 8, 2017 by retokromer						15
[v4] document sample range in ffv1 #24 opened on Sep 4, 2016 by dericed						3

ProTip! Follow long discussions with [comments:>50](#).

https://github.com/FFmpeg/FFV1/issues

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draft-ietf-cellar-matroska-01 Matroska Specifications	2018-07-26 165 pages	I-D Exists WG Document <i>Apr 2019</i>			
draft-ietf-cellar-tags-00 Matroska Tags	2018-07-17 20 pages	I-D Exists WG Document			

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Filters is:issue is:open

Labels Milestones

New issue

3 Open 53 Closed Author Labels Projects Milestones Assignee Sort

add handling of encodings others than binary enhancement format addition 2
#175 opened on Jan 26 by retokromer

Add a Rational Number type format addition 3
#164 opened on Aug 9, 2017 by robUx4

define convention for expressing EBML fragments in readable text enhancement format addition
#156 opened on Jul 14, 2017 by robUx4

ProTip! no:milestone will show everything without a milestone.

https://github.com/Matroska-Org/ebml-specification/issues

37 Open ✓ 38 Closed	Author -	Labels -	Projects -	Milestones -	Assignee -	Sort -
ProRes RAW profiles codec mapping format addition	#264	by Sami32				2
Add the WebM encryption elements enhancement format addition webm	#258	by robUx4				2
Please add AV1 support av1-mapping codec mapping enhancement	#229	by liyuxi				6
Block/SimpleBlock size equations are wrong bug clarifications	#213	by mbunkus				13
Cruft/Ideas in Menu section clarifications	#201	by ablwr				14
Rename Timecode* elements to Timestamp* enhancement	#197	by robUx4				5
clarify spec for A_PCM/FLOAT/IEEE clarifications codec mapping	#195	by dericed				1
define Matroska Player and Matroska Reader formatting	#194	by dericed				2
Makefile not building due to `<` error bug	#165	by ablwr				6
Attachments and Matroska Readers clarifications	#160	by ablwr				6
Generate the github website from the Makefile formatting	#146	by robUx4				
Fix internal documentation links formatting	#145	by robUx4				4
Split the specs in 3 parts formatting	#143	by robUx4				1
Specify PCM signedness codec mapping	#142	by mkver				3
How many Default Editions are allowed? clarifications	#141	by hubblec4				7
PDF of version 02	#132	by retokromer				2
range for LuminanceMax and LuminanceMin should be updated to hex floating point constants	#122	by dericed				12

37 Open ✓ 38 Closed	Author -	Labels -	Projects -	Milestones -	Assignee -	Sort -
support frame side data format addition	#270	opened 23 days ago				5
document rotation use case with ProjectionPoseRoll Element	#269	opened 25 days ago				11
ChapterSegmentEditionUID	#267	opened 26 days ago				
JPEG 2000 support codec mapping format addition	#261	opened on Sep 14				
Use `recurring` attribute on some level 1 elements clarifications	#257	opened on Aug 28				
Support cards like youtube ones clarifications format addition	#243	opened on Jul 18				6
CodecDelay should mention that data should be discarded clarifications enhancement	#242	opened on Jul 18				
Chapters Flags: wrong description clarifications	#238	opened on Jun 29				
Remove Control Track from the working docs clarifications enhancement	#234	opened on Jun 26				2
remove matroska.org direct links from ebml_matroska.xml enhancement formatting	#233	opened on Jun 26				
Nested-ordered chapters clarifications	#232	opened on Jun 18				2
EditionFlagDefault clarifications	#231	opened on May 31				13
EAC-3 support codec mapping	#230	opened on May 25				21
H.265/HEVC Support codec mapping enhancement	#228	opened on May 25				
H.264 support codec mapping enhancement	#227	opened on May 25				
Ideas to consider/add/ignore in Menus clarifications enhancement format addition	#219	opened on Jan 9				
Only one Edition with EditionFlagHidden Flag set to true clarifications format addition						

16 Open ✓ 193 Closed						
Av1 encryption sections	#283	opened 3 days ago				
assume values not found	#278	opened 13 days ago				
add block metadata structure	#276	opened 22 days ago				
WIP notes on conditional	#272	opened 22 days ago				
Add avs2 codec mapping	#249	opened on Jul 21				
Hard-Linking change	#245	opened on Jul 18				
New chapters.md	#244	opened on Jul 18				
Allow defining the default	#236	opened on Jun 27				
rename EditionFlagHidden	#235	opened on Jun 26				
RAWcooked reserved IDs	#223	opened on Mar 24				
All EditionFlagDefault Flags	#205	opened on Oct 30, 2017				
Adjust definition of "forced"	#158	opened on Jul 31, 2017				
info on storing/using forced	#115	opened on Mar 18, 2017				
add T_QUICKTIME codec	#112	opened on Mar 14, 2017				

```

drice:FFmpeg-derived drice$ git log --pretty=format:"%h%x09%an%x09%x09%" libavformat/matroskaenc.c
dcbd89e000 Siggia Regina avformat/matroskaenc: reserve free space for metadata on request
819e4e7979 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: reindent after the previous commit
8439656503 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: refactor checks for allowed codecs in WebM
794079e815 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: implement AVOutputFormat.query_codec for webm
14ac62f9af James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: remove unnecessary additional codec tags
a068594248 James Almer Revert "avformat/matroskaenc: write CodecPrivate in WebM"
4755b6e6d1 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: write CodecPrivate in WebM
cbe5c7ef38 Kagami Hiiragi lavf/matroska: Allow AV1 in WebM
de1b44c206 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: handle AV1 extradata in packet side data
2de5209d91 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: filter and reorder AV1 OBUs
022d4a2114 wm4 avformat/matroskaenc: do not write timebase as framerate
d401ba6b3d Carl Eugen Hoyos lavf/matroskaenc: Force the minimum value for -reserve_index_space to 2.
5f67073b4c James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: add missing allocation failure checks for stream durations
9924f1bc34 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: move some initialization checks to mkv_init
9d464dc3fc James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: actually enforce the stream limit
fd59207c1c James Almer Merge commit '827a05eaa9482e9ac2a17f7f2e42ead07c1d7574'
45121cbdda James Almer Merge commit '5d3953a5dcfd5f71391b7f34908517eb6f7e5146'
27b7800ba9 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: also write tags when output is WebM
0aa8fa963f Aleksandr Slobodeniuk avformat/riff.h : remove unused function parameter "const AVCodecTag *tags" of "void ff_put_bmp_header()"
2ba896fef7 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: also write chapters when output is WebM
7631f14bb3 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: check packet side data for AAC extradata updates
37cc1c1e91 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: add support for writing Content Light Level elements
a8b5f37501 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: don't try to update flac extradata if live streaming
4de591e6fb James Almer Merge commit '83548fe894cdb455cc127f754d09905b6d23c173'
827a05eaa9 James Almer matroskaenc: add support for Spherical Video elements
58eb0f57f6 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: add support for Spherical Video elements
1638d956a3 Carl Eugen Hoyos lavf/matroska: Support QDMC.
9ae762da7e Carl Eugen Hoyos lavf/matroska: Support codec ID V_FFV1 for demuxing.
1ad60e4e70 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: don't write DisplayUnit with value Unknown on WebM files
5d3953a5dc John Stebbins matroskaenc: factor ts_offset into block timecode computation
dce863421b James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: don't reserve more bytes than needed for the Colour master size
e4a1d87ef8 Sasi Inguva lavf/matroskaenc.c: Free dyn bufs in mkv_free. Fixes memory leaks when muxing fails.
e7dec52d4d Rostislav Pehlivanov matroskaenc: remove unofficial compliance on color information
935404923d Carl Eugen Hoyos Cosmetics: Reindent after last commit.
c723108e25 Carl Eugen Hoyos lavf/matroskaenc: Do not write two CodecID elements for rawvideo.
20e8be0c20 softworkz avformat/matroskaenc: Regression fix for invalid MKV headers
8c1342e631 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: write updated STREAMINFO metadata for FLAC streams if available
ee888cfbe7 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: postpone writing the Tracks master
98cae966c7 James Almer matroskaenc: write updated STREAMINFO metadata for FLAC streams if available
f4bf236338 James Almer matroskaenc: fix muxing AAC streams when using aac_adtstoasc bsf
5cb57131d3 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: use display aspect ratio for DisplayWidth and DisplayHeight when possible
bab6b60675 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: support writing Chroma Location elements
1a958f4eb0 Rodger Combs lavf/matroskaenc: don't try to modify the header when live-streaming
be28ce210d Rodger Combs lavf/matroskaenc: fix uninitialized read
6089c44a2a Adriano Pallavicino Fix build warnings due to misleading indentation
eabbc64728 James Almer avformat/matroskaenc: fix cue relative position values when CRC32 is enabled

```

```

drice:FFmpeg-derived drice$ git log --pretty=format:"%h%x09%an%x09%x09%" libavcodec/ffv1enc.c
a734ff4b0e Michael Niedermayer libavcodec/ffv1enc: minor cosmetic fix
7033654f7f Marton Balint Use AV_PIX_FMT_FLAG_ALPHA for detecting transparency where nb_components was used
d9706f79c1 Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Check that the crc + version combination is supported
b6fc09cdb4 Jérôme Martinez avcodec/ffv1: support of more pix_fmt
00035a6b4a Jérôme Martinez avcodec/ffv1enc: remove warning about transparency
fb580731c1 Jérôme Martinez avcodec/ffv1: Support for GBRAP10 and GBRAP12
698d5eb5bf Jérôme Martinez avcodec/ffv1: Support for RGBA64 and GBRAP16
e3d946b3f4 Jérôme Martinez avcodec/ffv1enc: mark RGB48 support as non-experimental
58e16a4f4b Jérôme Martinez avcodec/ffv1enc: mark RGB48 support as non-experimental
4ada428aae Martin Vignali avcodec: remove remaining uses of avcodec_get_chroma_sub_sample
0f8d3d8a46 Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: compute the max number of slices and limit by that
430d4f2bb5 Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Allow less than 2 rows of slices for low vertical resolution
4147bb9053 Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Try to choose slice count so that slice packet sizes are within the supported size
2f42aef3e4 Clément Bœsch Merge commit '17cb56b35672a2cd6ad7abe926e6cc772b8f4710'
38a7834bbb Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Allocate smaller packet if the worst case size cannot be allocated
cff1c0edaa Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Fix size of first slice
322568c079 Carl Eugen Hoyos lavc/ffv1: Support YUV4xxP12 and GRAY12.
f8247c0cce Carl Eugen Hoyos lavc/ffv1enc: Support pix_fmt GRAY10.
c1173437fc Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Fix storing RGB48 without explicitly set level
17cb56b356 Diego Biurrun ffv1: Remove broken disabled cruft
62f5e601aa Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Add RGB48 support
a95fdac4c6 Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: do not offset null pointers
87da118898 Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Factor rice high depth check out
ce2217b25e Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1: add AV_PIX_FMT_GBRP16 support
74314f1f5f Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1: template functions to allow data types different from int16_t
c1bfeda5a3 Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Fix assertion failure with non zero bits per sample
fe6e5cbea7 Luca Barbato ffv1: Remove version 2 and mark version 3 as non-experimental
9204a84998 Clément Bœsch Merge commit '5c31eaa9998b2185e0aa04d11adff128498dc14a'
403a53c60e James Almer avcodec/ffv1enc: silence warning about deprecated coded_frame
5c31eaa999 Alexandra Hájková Remove unnecessary get_bits.h #includes and add missing headers where needed.
5b0d4c247a Derek Buitenhuis Merge commit '96c373c7704aeb1cc1d2c275fbb5d7177665589'
21f9468402 Derek Buitenhuis avutil: Rename FF_CEIL_COMPAT to AV_CEIL_COMPAT
96c373c770 Vittorio Giovara lavc: Move context_model to codec private options
e8bc642202 Clément Bœsch lavu: add AV_CEIL_RSHIFT and use it in various places
3843e52cb4 Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Support AV_PIX_FMT_YA8
2d2b41d169 Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Fix 2 pass mode with the default rc table
1c878474fb Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: unbreak -coder option
2630f7f709 Hendrik Leppkes Merge commit 'be0ec832c519427cd92218abac77dafdc1d5487'
be0ec832c Vittorio Giovara lavc: Deprecate coder_type and its symbols
fb99ef0bd3 Clément Bœsch avcodec: use AV_OPT_TYPE_BOOL in a bunch of places
bba2488f07 Derek Buitenhuis Merge commit '4bb1070c154e49d35805fbcddac9c9e92f702ef96'
4bb1070c15 Vittorio Giovara ffv1: Explicitly name the coder type
aa6c43f3fd Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1: separate slice_count from max_slice_count
72db5e96fc Michael Niedermayer avcodec/ffv1enc: Fix error message when the requested version does not support the requested features
5d8e836d0e Hendrik Leppkes Replace all remaining occurrences of step/depth_minus1 and offset_plus1
f0af25ae11 Timothy Gu ffv1: Add missing ff_ prefixes

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Thanks

<https://datatracker.ietf.org/wg/cellar>

<https://github.com/ffmpeg/ffv1>

<https://github.com/Matroska-Org/matroska-specification>

<https://github.com/Matroska-Org/ebml-specification>

@dericed 2018-10-25 #nttw3